

The biology of oxidative stress: a comprehensive mini-review

Elena Stouppenou

Medical School, University of Cyprus

ABSTRACT

Oxidative stress is one of the main causes of pathogenesis in the human body and has been found to be related to diseases such as atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, cancer, ischemia, neurodegenerative diseases and chronic kidney disease. To this end, this comprehensive mini-review explores the causes of oxidative stress, its effects on different biomolecules and biological processes as well as ways of combating oxidative stress.

KEYWORDS: Oxidative stress, respiratory chain, pathogenesis

Introduction

Oxidative stress is defined as an imbalance between oxidizing agents and antioxidant mechanisms of a cell causing damage within it. Based on this definition, oxidative stress can be caused by an increase in oxidizing factors, by difficulty in isolating them and by external factors. Oxidizing agents are considered reactive forms of nitrogen, oxygen and free radicals. These substances are necessary for the body in very small amounts but in greater amounts they can induce severe cell damage [1].

Oxygen is one of the most important components for aerobic organisms and contributes to the execution of important metabolic processes. Specifically, oxygen is the final acceptor of electrons in the respiratory chain which takes place in the

mitochondria. Oxygen is reduced to water with the help of cytochrome oxidase. However, some oxygen molecules "escape" from this process and are reduced to intermediate compounds with an odd number of electrons. These compounds are not free radicals but can contribute to the production of free radicals [2, 3].

Oxidative stress causes adverse conditions in the body. It can cause damage to the DNA, proteins, lipids and carbohydrates. First, it alters the structure of several enzymes and proteins and thus affects their function. Also, the DNA can undergo mutations and the lipids that make up cell membranes and lipoproteins undergo peroxidation. The result of all these damages is the appearance of diseases and pathological conditions such as atherosclerosis, diabetes mellitus, cancer, ischemia, neurodegenerative diseases and chronic kidney disease [2, 4].

Free radicals

As mentioned above, oxidative stress is caused by the production of free radicals. Free radicals are atoms or groups of atoms that have one or more unpaired electrons in the outer electronic layer. Free radicals can be produced in two ways: homolytic cleavage and redox reactions. Homolytic cleavage occurs when a covalent bond of a normal molecule is broken into two products which contain an unpaired electron. Here the presence of energy is required, such as UV radiation, ionizing radiation or heat. On the other hand, redox reaction occur when an electron is added or removed from normal molecule forming a free radical. In these reactions no energy is needed [5].

Fenton's reaction

Figure 1 displays Fenton's reaction which is one of the basic ways of producing free hydroxyl radicals. It can take place in the presence of other metals such as copper and nickel. However, the reaction with iron is more common since it is found in larger quantities in the human body [4, 6, 7].

Figure 1: The Fenton reaction

Effects of free radicals

5.1 Effect on lipids

When oxidizing agents act on lipids then the lipids will undergo peroxidation [8]. The steps of lipid peroxidation are:

1. Initially, an active free radical detaches from a methyl group. Hence a fatty acid free radical is created,

2. Due to the instability of this free radical, recombination of electrons from the adjacent double bonds are formed,

3. The new free radical is more stable and prevents reaction with oxygen forming a peroxide radical.

4. Peroxides accumulate and are broken down through different mechanisms. The breakdown products such as malondialdehyde and 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal contribute to the continuation of the cycle of reactions.

The end result of this process is cellular oxidation membranes and cell death [6, 7].

5.2 Effect on DNA and RNA molecules

The main radicals that cause oxidative damage to genetic material are hydroxyl radicals. When transition metals are bound to the DNA, such as iron, then free hydroxyl radicals are formed near DNA molecules through the Fenton reaction. If these radicals are generated away from the DNA then due to their high activity they cannot travel and reach the DNA. But often, reactive roots diffuse away from the place of their creation and react with other molecules to form secondary products that can reach the DNA and react with it [1, 6].

Oxidation of genetic material has various effects such as segregation of chains, the exchange of sister chromatids and changes in nitrogenous bases (i.e., mutations) [9]. Additionally, free radicals have the ability to react with core proteins to form other free radicals that attach with the genetic material and affect genetic repair and biosynthesis processes. Mitochondrial DNA is the one most affected by oxidizing agents since the respiratory chain which is the main source of free radical formation occurs in the mitochondria [1, 6].

5.3 Effect on proteins

One of the major free radicals affecting proteins is the oxygen free radical which reacts with sulfur complexes located on prosthetic groups of proteins [9].

Additionally, some protein amino acids have thiol groups on their surface. Free radicals react with these groups forming thiol radicals.

When oxygen is sufficient then they react with it forming sulfoperoxide roots. However, when oxygen is present in small amounts then the thiol radicals, they react with each other creating disulfide bonds.

Finally, there is a possibility of free radicals forming in side chains amino acids by changing position in the protein. This results in the formation of covalent bonds affecting the structure and function of certain proteins [6].

Discussion and conclusions

As seen in this review, oxidative stress has adverse effects on human vcells by negatively affecting the basic biomolecules which are the lipids, lipoproteins, proteins and genetic material. First, it decreases the fluidity of cell membranes, their permeability is increased [8]. Moreover, oxidative modification of proteins results in transformation of active centers of enzymes affecting their function and specifically, the oxidation of histidine contributes to the aging process. Finally, the DNA can undergo mutations as a result oxidative stress. All this results in cell death [5].

However, these oxidizing agents can be treated at first stage with antioxidant mechanisms, thus preventing the occurrence of diseases such as atherosclerosis, cancer, diabetes and neurodegenerative diseases

There are specific enzymes with antioxidant activity which can combat oxidative stress. In addition, there are antioxidants that bind

transition metals, preventing the Fenton reaction and thus the formation of free hydroxyl radicals. Iron is bound by lactoferrin, transferrin and ferritin while copper is bound by ceruloplasmin. Finally, vitamins such as A, C, E, niacin flavin and thiamine and other nutrients that we take in through the food pyramid contribute to combating the action of oxidants [3, 5].

Based on the Mediterranean food pyramid, antioxidants are found in full abundance in fruits, vegetables, legumes and nuts [3]. So, one diet that does not contain these ingredients increases the person's chances of getting it oxidative stress. Therefore, it is imperative that people eat properly so that they are protected from the diseases caused by oxidative stress since prevention is the best cure [2].

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